
Climate Change: Youth and Gender Perception, Attitude and Behaviour

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Abstract India is a developing country with a huge population due to which a lot of emphasis is given on India when talking of climate change. Climate change is having a huge impact on the whole globe and especially, India, where till today, many people depend on rains for their crops in rural India. The recently published Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), Climate Change 2021 by the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) summarises that now scientists are more confident than ever before that human activities have triggered climate change. In particular, as a consequence of human activities, the planet has warmed at a rate never experienced before in the planet's history especially in the past 2,000 years. According to the report, compared to the pre-industrial period of 1850-1900 the global surface temperature of Earth is 1.09 degree Celsius higher. The principal factor of hot weather extremes that have become more intense and frequent since the 1950s is human influence and these extremes would have been improbable without it. The report is certain that emissions due to human activities are the main driver, on the global scale, of the changes in cold and hot extremes, and of ocean acidification and warming. By the end of this century, the average global temperatures will rise continuously and could rise up to 5.7 degrees Celsius as compared to 1850-1900. Also, the 1.5 degrees Celsius and 2 degrees Celsius mark of average global surface temperature will be breached much earlier. All this will have severe social, economical and political consequences in India. Every part of the society will have huge implications of the changing climate, especially youths, who will be at the forefront in facing the impacts and even in taking actions too. So, a study on perceptions, attitude and behaviour of people about climate change with a focus on youth and gender is pertinent in this scenario in India.

Keywords Climate Change, Youth, Gender Perception, Attitude, Behaviour

Introduction

Individuals are going to be the ultimate actors who inspire, enact, guide and initiate the much needed cuts in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions to slow down the ongoing global warming and who evolve, develop and implement the sustainable adaptive responses to minimize its severe impacts. Acknowledging these roles does not mean a disregard for the larger contexts in which individuals act, nor do we try to place ill-suited responsibility on individuals. In responding to climate change, what matters is an individual's level of emotional and cognitive engagement as well as what that engagement is affected by, or leads to by, behavioural changes and political and civic activities. In order to effectively mitigate, incentive programs, future regulations, policies and taxation schemes may call up individuals to alter their travel modes, leisure activities, energy-consuming habits, and could possibly include calls for reconciliation to individuals' lifestyle, reproductive and food choices.

In Ajzen's (1985) theory of planned behaviour, beliefs are used to predict an individual's intention to engage in behaviour. Behavioural intentions have been defined by Ajzen (2002) as indication of an individual's readiness to perform a given behaviour, based on attitudinal beliefs and perceived behavioural control, and are assumed to be an immediate predecessor to behavior. The theory of planned behaviour was developed from the Expectancy

Value Models (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980). According to this theory, if people evaluate the suggested behaviour as positive (attitude) there is a higher intention (motivation) to perform the behaviour. Many studies have confirmed a high correlation of attitudes to behavioural intention and subsequently to behaviour (Sheppard, Hartwick & Warshaw, 1988). One study measuring attitudes toward human - induced climate change found students who have a more accepting attitude toward climate change are more likely to express a willingness to take action (Sinatra *et al.*, 2012). Motivation to act on one's beliefs is an important step in enacting change (Sinatra *et al.*, 2012). One goal of educating students about climate change and human impact on the environment is to create responsible adults who will make informed decisions regarding the environment in the future. Findings suggest that students who have more favourable attitudes toward the idea of human - induced climate change are more likely to report a willingness to take action (Sinatra *et al.*, 2012). Other researchers have found that increasing environmental content knowledge in individuals results in more positive attitudes and responsible behaviour toward the environment (Bradley, Waliczek, & Zajicek, 1999; McMillan, Wright & Beazley, 2004) while one multi-national study was unable to show that knowledge about climate change was related to environment-related attitudes (Dijkstra & Goedhart, 2012). Knowledge is a forerunner to beliefs that may or may not lead to actions. Environmental attitudes consist of beliefs, affect, and behavioural intentions that combine to illustrate attitudes toward environmentally related activities or issues (Schultz *et al.*, 2005; DeWaters & Powers, 2013). People have different kinds of perceptions about climate change and in fact, a school of thought believes such that climate change does not exist. But the severe changes in climate with each passing season, for example-droughts and floods, have altered the perception of people towards climate change (Frondel *et al.*, 2017; Rankoana, 2016). Childhood is the canvas that forms the basis of the beliefs and ideologies of the individual in the future. If a child is taught positive environmental behaviours that the child cares for the environment from an early age in his/her life, this affects the child's behaviour later in life ((Ballantyne, Connell, & Fien, 2006; Chawla, 1999; Meinhold & Malkus, 2005). Children receive more information about climate change from social media rather than schools (Robertson & Barbosa, 2015) and this is attributed to the lack of related information and content in academic curriculum. (Choi *et al.*, 2010)

Climate change is seen as a threat that would affect future generations and that's why it is not taken that seriously it needs to be. (Leiserowitz *et al.*, 2013) Climate change policies have not been enough to make people aware about climate change that it transcends into action. (Westerhoff and Robinson, 2013; Randall, 2009; Lejano *et al.*, 2013)

Youth in the age group of 15-29 years comprise 27.5% of the population. At present, about 34% of India's Gross National Income (GNI) is contributed by the youth, aged 15-29 years. At the same time, there exists a huge potential to increase the contribution of this class of the nation's citizenry by increasing their participation in climate change mitigation and adaptation in the coming years to tackle the problem of climate change.

Climate change is a disaster that shall affect everybody from micro-organisms to humans, rich to poor and all genders. The effects also vary over time and scale. From a gender perspective, many studies have said that women are affected more by the disasters like drought, flood etc. especially, in developing countries, where the women have less education, less skill and due to this, they have little access to the needed information pre- and post- disaster. Any loss in job can further aggravate the problem of poverty. It has been said that the social construct is such that it keeps the women at a vulnerable state of danger and higher female mortality rates due to disaster. (Neumayer and Plumper, 2007). Women are generally seen as the victims of the disasters but they can also be contributors in the problem solving as they are closer to nature and have knowledge regarding the local scenarios and changes. These considerations are generally not taken into account by decision makers and planners. (WEDO, 2007). The use of natural resources and social interactions are closely intertwined and can be seen in the lives of local men and women. This is because of the gender- specific roles and both genders play diverse roles in the use and management of resources.

Women have been often more associated with nature under the broad term, Ecofeminism, in which resemblance is shown between the nourishing nature of both. The term ecofeminism was coined by Franciosed' Eaubonne (1994) in 1974 to tell about the importance of women in environmental management and changes. (Besthorn and McMillen, 2002) There have been many ecofeminists and women social critics, writers like Rachel Carson

(The Silent Spring). Women's participation in environmental issues has been highlighted in various international treaties like UNCED. According to a Swedish Government Report, 2007; it has been shown that women in the North, in the developed countries, have lower carbon footprint than males. This can be attributed to their lifestyle choices at everyday household level or in travel etc. (Owren, 2012)

A detailed insight on the relation between youth and adults, and gender on climate change will be seen in the survey report.

Objectives

The objectives of the survey report are:

- identify the structure of climate change perceptions;
- give insight into public engagement with climate change responses and policies;
- identify the role of individual socio-political values and other individual level factors;
- tracking public understanding of this problem;
- Understanding the relation and perception of gender with respect to climate change;
- Identifying solutions that could be taken for accelerating the progress of climate change; and
- Viewing success towards climate change as according to the masses.

Methodology

This study consisted of a national survey with mostly Indians and one international participant from Boston, USA. The total number of participants of the survey is 235. The research method involves use of a Google form questionnaire which was circulated in networks of Centre for Youth organization (C4Y) and the responses were diverse which were later graphed and calculated statistically with MS Excel. Also, the responses were grouped in two ways: one, between men and women to analyze the differences or similarities between gender perceptions and two, between youth and adults to analyze the differences or similarities between perceptions of youth and adults and males and females.

Results and Discussion

Category of Respondents

It has been seen that all the respondents are literate and are either students, employed or self- employed. Majority of the females are employed and males are self- employed. The Mostly, respondents were of the age of 21 to 40. The division is as shown in the table. The number of females participating in the quiz is more than the males.

Age	Number of Female Subjects	Number of Male Subjects	
10--20	29	8	GROUP 1
21-30	51	25	
31-40	17	23	GROUP 2
41-50	24	16	
51-60	31	5	
61-70	3	2	

1. Youth vs Adult Analysis

The 235 total participants of the survey were divided among two groups according to their age. Group one consists of all the participants less than the age of 30 and group 2 consists of the participants aged 30 or more than 30. Thirty was chosen as a dividing age because National Youth Policy, 2014 considers youth in India to be of the age group 15-29 years. Group 1 has 105 participants and group 2 has the remaining 135 participants.

In response to first question 1, although both groups believe that career is the top most priority for youths. But when we analyse the priority between the environmental concerns of climate change and clean air, it is found that for Group 1 climate change (10 participants ~ 9.5%) is a bigger concern than clean air (3 participants ~ 2.85%). On the other hand, Group 2 considers clean air as a bigger problem than climate change.

This difference between the priority of climate change and clean air might be an indication that adults are more concerned about the short-term issues (as that of clean air) and youths are more concerned about their future and long term impacts of climate change.

Both the groups majorly perceive climate change as a threat of a great extent for youths. There was no significant difference between the level of understanding of both the groups as per their ratings which suggests that youths are getting informed about the topic extensively in the recent years through school or college curriculum and also through the influence of social media.

It is worth mentioning that most of the adults (120 participants ~ 92.3%) have experienced firsthand the impact of climate change in terms of weather patterns. None of the Group 2 participants chose “NO” as a response. Although most of the youths (90 participants ~ 85.7%) replied positively to the question, their percentage is lower than that of adults. In this group, 5 participants and 10 participants chose “NO” and “Can’t say” as a response, respectively. This might represent a section of society which is not aware about the issue of climate change or couldn’t relate the learnings of climate change in daily life.

The participants of both the groups discuss climate change “often” or “occasionally” in their friend or family circle. This suggests that people are concerned about climate change and they communicate on the topic with their closed ones. This not only has the potential to increase the attitude and behaviour of the participants more positively but it also has the potential to increase information about climate change and thus the attitude or behaviour of the recipients of these discussions.

All the participants have taken several measures to control their emissions or capture their emissions through various activities. The lockdowns induced by the spread of COVID-19 pandemic forced humanity to change its lifestyles. The participants undertook several positive changes in lifestyles to adopt greener practices during pandemic. The response to if they would continue these practices in future was encouraging for both groups. Most of the youths (~75%) as well as adults (~65%) chose to continue taking these measures to a great extent in the future. Here too, the higher percentage of youths willing to continue taking these measures suggest that youths are more worried about their future and they want to contribute individually in reducing the impacts of climate change.

A majority (~60%) of the respondents in both groups think that consumerist lifestyle is one of the important factors contributing to GHG emissions. This is a good sign that people understand the carbon footprint associated with goods that we consume in daily life. But almost every product in India doesn’t provide any information about its carbon footprint due to which even if a consumer wants to make low carbon choices, he or she can’t make it easily.

During pandemic, work/study from home was the only option left for most of the people. This has significantly reduced the carbon emissions due to transportation and emissions related to electricity and infrastructure use at the offices or institutes. This might be a reason that the majority of the respondents, more or less two-thirds of total in both groups, believe that this “new normal” can be beneficial for the environmental well-being. The respondents who have chosen “No” or “Undecided” would be worried about the increased electricity use and its related emissions to make a definite choice.

Air pollution is a major environmental issue in many cities in India especially in Delhi due to stubble crop burning. Delhi government has tried an Odd-even scheme to tackle the air pollution caused due to transportation. Further, switching off engines on red-light is advertised in the frontline newspapers and TV channels to save fuel and the environment by reducing fuel’s overuse. It is worth noticing that Adults have more faith in these initiatives by the government as 24 respondents (~18.5%) of Group 2 believe that these programs are “Greatly successful” whereas only 9 respondents (~8.5%) of Group 1 believed these programs are “Greatly successful”. The youths believe more that such programs are only “moderately successful”. These responses indicate a decreasing belief of youths in government initiatives. Further, this indication is confirmed by the response to the question where participants were asked if the governments or authorities are doing enough to reduce GHG emissions. Only 15 participants (~14.28%) of group 1 replied positively with a “Yes” and on the other hand 44 participants (~41.5%) of group 2 chose “Yes” as a response.

There is a significant difference between the attitudes of youths and adults towards government's intention and initiatives to tackle climate change. This trend of less belief in government by the youth might be due to the recent youth movements who have targeted all the governments and politicians around the world for not taking enough and strong decisions to safeguard their right to a healthy environment. This emerging trend can be a matter of great concern in future as governments will require support from the public to implement their environmental policies and public participation is must to make such policies successful.

In the response to the question of “From the list of several provided stakeholders, whom youth can influence the most on climate change?”, it is interesting to know that the youth believes in youth. The youth has a positive attitude that they can influence people of the same age. They might be motivated by the recent youth movements where youths around the world have been successful in bringing the youths together on the issue of climate change and demand stronger and quick climate actions from the persons in authority. These movements and its social media outreach enable the youth to think that they can like the other youth leaders; they also can influence their peers.

Also, it is a well known fact that the youths have more influence from peers in daily life. This might be an additional factor behind this response from the youths. But it is important to mention here that although adults think that youth can majorly influence youths (32 participants), they have an almost similar inclination towards youths capability to influence governments (27 participants), educational institutions (28 participants) and civil societies (22 participants). But the youth believes that they can influence majorly in their personal space such as youths (45 participants) and educational institutions (24 participants).

2. Gender and Attitudes Towards Climate Change

More positive attitudes towards science have been reported in male students than female students (Dijkstra & Goedhart, 2012) while others have found that girls have a high positive attitude towards science on par with boys. (Archer, DeWitt, Osborne, Dillon, Willis & Wong, 2012) Females have been found to have more positive attitudes towards environmental issues than boys. (Davidson & Freudenburg, 1996; Gardos & Dodd, 1995; Leppanen, Haahla, Lensu & Kuitunen, 2012) and have been proactive in protection of the environment (Tosunoglu, 1993). The background of subjects was found to be equally important as the girls had positive behaviour as their parents as opposed to boys who had a more negative one. (Leppanen, 2012)

➤ Survey Analysis

1. What is the most important priority for Youth?

Among the females, ~41% of them said that they gave preference to career, followed healthy lifestyle, education, clean air, climate change and good governance.

Whereas, males preferred career (52%), followed by education, healthy lifestyle, good governance, clean air, and climate change at least preference.

Both genders prefer career over all choices in life and prefer climate change towards least bothered side of the spectrum.

2. To what extent climate change is a matter of concern for youth?

According to the survey results, both males (65%) and females (69%) believe that the climate change is an important matter of concern for youth. And a good percentage of males and females also believe that the climate

change is a matter of concern for youth but only to some extent. All the people who consider that climate change is not concerning youth have opted for career as the biggest priority in the above question.

3. Rate your understanding level about climate change issues.

35% females rated their understanding in the category of good, followed by very good understanding rating,

average, excellent and not so good rating.

Among males, majority of the 33% males rated their understanding of climate change as very good, followed by good, excellent, average and not so good.

Both genders rate for their proportionally good understanding of climate change.

4. Have you noticed the effects of climate change in terms of weather patterns first hand?

When the subjects were asked for the noticeable weather changes at first hand, both genders replied positively at

around high percentage of 90%. A little fraction of the subjects, i.e., 10% females and 5% males were not really sure on the aspect. These subjects rated their knowledge of climate change at three levels, not so good, average and most commonly, good.

5. Climate change is real and is continuously happening. How often you talk about it in your friend/family circle?

In the question on how often subject talk about climate change in theirsocial circle, 57% females and 52% said often, whereas 40% females and 43% males talk occasionally about climate change. The 2% females and 5% males never talk about climate change in their social circle. This last lot of never talking males and females never talking about climate change does not mean these few individuals are not talking about climate change but rather, this signifies that the whole groups related to these individuals are not talking about climate change. This data may involve a large number of people. Hence, the reasons of such attitude towards climate change when it

is such a burning and needed topic of today’s global scenario. These individuals are the individuals who have rated their knowledge on climate change as average or good.

This means a good knowledge is present among the population as per the survey but the implementation of the knowledge is seen lacking in terms of communication. An efficient communication is said to be the most powerful tool when it comes to problem solving and mass propagation of a cause. This ‘Never talk attitude’ about climate change means that we as a society are lagging in the widespread communication of a need of the hour and this attitude is more among males. More research needs to be done to look into the causes.

Shifting the focus to the larger population who talk about climate change often or occasionally present a ray of hope of climate change mitigation

6. As an individual, what contributions have you made to slow down the causes or effects of climate change at your own level or community level? (Multiple Response)

No revolution is complete just by knowledge, but by consistent efforts and results. The subjects in the survey are found to be involved in a lot of activities towards climate change mitigation like 17% females reduced water consumption at home as opposite to 8% males, 16% females and 14% males optimized electricity use at homes, 15% females and 16% males planted trees and taken care of them, 10% females and 9% males participated in school and other activities, 4% females and 7% males took part in civil society activities, 5% females and 7% males participated in online campaigning followed by 10% females and 8% males adopting sustainable practices in their lifestyles. Pertaining to in-house and school activities, more females are found to be proactive and on online platforms and outdoors, more males were found to be proactive. Research needs to be done on a larger data set to see the reliability of this data.

7. To what extent you would continue taking these measures?

When coming to the question of continuation of the measures adopted by the subjects of the survey for better

environment, almost consistent results were found among both genders where around 70% of individuals were willing to continue with these to a large extent and about 30% willing to some extent and only about 1-2% of the subjects interested to a very less extent in maintaining the consistency.

8. Do you think consumerist lifestyle is one of the important factors contributing in greenhouse gases emission?

Today’s time means fast-paced life in which consumerism is at peak, especially, visible in the textile industry where the fashion continuously keeps updating to new within short stretches of time and clothes are not work their lifetime but, until, the trend persists. Industries are run, transportation is done based on the demand of the product in the market, making consumerism the culprit of green house gas emissions. The female and male subjects of the survey, both agreed that the consumeristic lifestyle is responsible for a lot of green house gas emission at a large extent. 65% females agreed to this and 52% males. 34% females and 43% males considered the consumeristic lifestyles responsible for green house gas emissions only to some extent followed by a lesser proportion of subjects who considered the same cause-effect to a very less extent. It is worth noting that the degree of compliance may vary among the subjects with the fact that today’s lifestyle of ‘use and throw’ is responsible for high ecological footprint but none of them denied the fact.

9. What are the changes you have made in your lifestyle for adopting green practices in last one year especially during pandemic? (Multiple Response)

Some easy initiatives that can be taken by anybody for growing towards sustainable life are eating seasonal fruits and vegetables, using cycling, or walking for shorter distances, eating less junk packaged food, avoiding non-vegetarian diet, buying from local markets, and buying star-labelled products. These all measured are associated with decreasing the ecological footprint to a large extent by cutting the transportation requirement, using more efficient products like star-labelled ones use less energy and create less pollution, hence, energy conservation. The results were similar for both genders. They preferred eating seasonal fruits and vegetables, followed by eating less junk packaged food, buying from local markets, using cycling, or walking for shorter distances, avoiding non-vegetarian diet and at last, using star-labelled products with 14% males and 10% females interested in same.

10. To what extent are you willing to continue making these changes in your lifestyle for reducing your carbon footprints on the planet?

To reduce the carbon footprints on the planet, around 70% of males and females are interested in making the lifestyle changes a part of their lives with 71% females and 68% males to a great extent. Around 27% males and females are willing to make lifestyle changes to some extent and a very small population fraction willing to a very less extent. The logics behind these choices are ambiguous

11. The pandemic has compelled us to adopt an alternative "online" way of life including travel. Do you think this new normal should be continued after pandemic for environmental wellbeing?

Travelling is an outdoor activity and amidst Corona time, it took a shape of indoor activity via. travel online. When considering the positive impacts of online travel on environment, 63% females and 72% males considered

it good to be continued after pandemic also. 12% females and 14% males responded negatively and 25% females and 14% males were unclear on their take.

12. How successful do you think the government's initiatives such as odd even for two & four wheelers or engine switch off at the traffic signal are successful in healing environment?

Only 12% females and 18% males consider that the government's initiatives such as odd even for two & four wheelers or engine switch off at the traffic signal are greatly successful in healing environment whereas 64%

females and 53% males think that the initiatives are moderately successful in healing environment. 21% females and males consider these initiatives as less successful in healing environment. A considerable proportion of individuals (3% females and 8% males) believe that these policies and initiatives have not made any difference in healing the environment. The environmental changes are visible only after long times. Hence, research needs to be done to see whether there has been any effect on the overall environment quality.

13. Do you practice these initiatives?

56% females and 63% males confirmed that they practice these initiatives always. It is a good hope towards a changing future towards good. 38% females and 31% males said that they do practice the initiatives but sometimes. 6% males and females denied practicing the initiatives. These denials for practicing the green initiatives pose the challenge for researchers, politicians and to all of us as a society for which solutions need to be brought up.

14. Do you think the national/ world governments and climate authorities doing enough in reducing greenhouse gases emission?

When asked about the national/ world governments and climate authorities doing enough in reducing

greenhouse gases emission, a huge proportion of population (49% females and 59% males). Males were more on the denial than the females. This sets a challenge for researchers, policy makers to look-into the possible reasons and mitigate them. 32% females and 21% males believe that the governments are doing enough to serve the purpose. 20% of the subjects don't have a say in this respect.

15. From the following stakeholders, whom youth can influence the most on climate change?

‘Who do you think has the most influence on climate change?’ Is a very pertinent question in the times of influencing and social media. An influence can drive people towards good or bad. Both male and female subjects of the survey said that the youth has the highest influence on climate change and can be very influential in climate change mitigation. Recent incidents like Fridays for Future, Climate Youth Strikes depict a similar picture. In fact, youth has forced governments to review their policies for a better approach like the construction projects that were given allowance in 2020 in India at various locations in India like Mumbai, Goa etc.

The next important influencer for the subjects is educational institutions. Government and civil society rank next in the influencing list followed by children, neighbourhood, and business. It is said that the primary teachers are

family, society, and school. These three have been well- seen as influencers in climate change also. Well, every change starts with awareness and need to bring the change.

Limitations

- All the respondents are literate and so, do not symbolize the whole population of India which is a mixture of literate and illiterate people who may not have any idea about climate change consciously.
- Some setbacks of the study are that the questionnaire could not interact with the respondents at one-to-one basis and hence could not determine the actual reasons of their respective choices.
- Also, the questions were close ended for the ease of the record and that limited a myriad of ways in which one can and/or does contribute to limit their carbon footprints and save the environment.
- The questionnaire could have been more exhaustive to get to know about more insights of the respondents.

Conclusion

Any attempt by industry or government to address greenhouse gas emissions and global warming will require public understanding or recognition of the problem and willingness to bear the costs of remedies. This study is an attempt to analyse the understanding, attitudes, perceptions and behaviour of individuals. The youth vs. adult analysis gives us some important insights about the differences and similarities between them in various aspects. Youths and adults share similarities in matters of understanding of climate change and taking actions at individual levels. They have felt the impacts of climate change in their daily lives. But the differences between these groups are important to be considered for future references and research. There is a significant difference in perspective of taking and continuing greener actions between them. This might indicate towards the scenario where adults perceive climate change as a distant issue which doesn't require prompt and sustained actions. The youth seems more concerned about its future and believe in taking climate actions at individual levels and even sustaining these actions. This points towards a positive attitude of youth on climate action and also suggests that youth, in the future, will readily change his behaviour as required. Further research in this aspect is suggested with some specific questions in the survey to analyse the risk perceptions of adults vs. Youth and the link between the risk perceptions and the attitudes or behaviour induced by it.

The youths have less confidence in government than the adults. Youth also feels that government initiatives are not up to the mark in combating the different environmental challenges. In the light of recent youth climate movements, research is suggested in the near future that addresses the question of faith in government policies and intentions to combat climate change between youths and adults. In future, the support from all sections of the society will be necessary to support the decisions and policies of the government and we can't afford to miss out an important section of society in this regard. Youths are key stakeholders in the climate change discussions and their role will increase in coming years. Their perception and attitude will be defining the climate policy and action paths. They must have positive attitudes in this regard towards the government policies to make them more efficient.

The youth also believes that they can influence their peers more rather than the government to take climate actions in future. This is an important finding in the background of recent years' surge in youth climate activism. The popularity of Fridays For Future, Climate strikes and Greta Thunberg have set a tone of urgency among youths and brought them together on the issue. This ongoing era of communication revolution has provided youth with ease of internet and social media use, which they are using to connect to youths all over the world and making their voices heard internationally. That's why youth believes that it will be easier to mobilise youths to take climate action.

Thus, it is suggested that in near future, research should focus on the how the perceptions, attitude and behaviours of the youth differ with that of adults. The findings must be utilised to minimise this gap between them, so that both the age groups can understand each other and work in synergy to combat the global problem of climate change.

There exist a lot of similarities and dissimilarities in the way, both the genders perceive climate change and its related aspects. Both these genders have a basic common understanding of climate change and a baseline

population from both the genders believe in all facts about climate change but the proportion of population varies. The basic difference seen is the connection between males and females with environment in which it is seen that the concept of ecofeminism is deemed true. The very first difference lies in the number of females who participated in the survey is far more than the males (154:79). Half of the subjects have career as their priority and climate change is a concern for them to a large extent as majority of them are witnessing the effects of climate change in their daily lives and are having a good knowledge of climate change but at the same time, climate change and air quality are least priority for the subjects as in the priority list provided. A good 5% of males and 1% of females never talk about climate change in their groups, in other words, whole group does not talk about climate change as a whole. This needs to be seen into. Because it is not about a small population but a lagging population. If even a small proportion of population is lagging, it will be a hurdle for overall population as choosing eco- friendly options can be difficult at first like taking bicycle to the market as it is attached to lesser sophistication and ease and, also, a status symbol. Hence, if any portion of population is not willing, they need to be taken along one way or the other. Also, talking about climate change is the least people can do and if population is lagging at the least, achieving the highest goal can be a challenge.

All the subjects are literate being either students or employed. All of them have been associated with one or the other activity related to environment betterment. Most subjects are involved in indoor activities like reduced water consumption at home, using energy efficient options at home and lesser engaging in civic society activities and overall green lives. These the steps we need to inculcate but are not even close to what is required in the present times. Also, we need to consider that these are the literate people with good understanding of climate change and are taking actions that are very preliminary and represent a portion of whole population of India. A large majority of them consider taking these steps in the long run and think that the consumeristic lifestyle is a major factor contributing to the climate change. The subjects have taken steps related to lifestyle like eating local fruits and vegetables, avoiding junk food, measures that can be done in everyday life and most of them are willing continue with these measures in long run. The subjects also felt that online travel is a good measure to continue with in future times and feel that initiatives like odd- even have only moderately been successful in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and most of them abide by these rules and initiatives more of the times. Also, the subjects believe that the governments and International organizations have been unable to meet the needs to mitigate climate change and in reducing green house gas emissions. Yet, this is not a good sign of what we have done but a good sign of the potential of actions we still hold. Will makes the way, needs generates the will and now is the time of need; the need of action; which according to the subjects is highly influenced by youth, education, civic societies, and government.

In the survey, it has been seen that a high pressure lies on the government along with a high amount of dissatisfaction from the government as per the subjects. Subjects are willing to take actions at their level and, also, follow them in long-run. Another interesting finding is that subjects have good knowledge of climate change. They have highest priority for career and least priority for climate. But they understand the importance of good and healthy environment but are not able to serve the purpose due to lack of opportunities in this field or other preoccupations. Every problem is an opportunity and so, if career opportunities can be stemmed out of climate change mitigation and related fields, plus, there are government jobs in this field and government gets involved actively in this prerequisite of the present scenario, all problems like resentment against government, unemployment, lesser career options and most importantly, climate change can be tackled at one time.

This not only points to a need for further refinement in our knowledge of public understanding and engagement, but also simply to accept that no one theory will explain the variation in human experience of climate change and action in response to it. Surveys particular about a personality trait are needed to increase the knowledge of the differences highlighted in the report and future policies need to be framed and aligned to these findings for their maximum efficiency.

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